

Introducing the aWISH project: Animal Welfare Indicators at the SlaughterHouse

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aWISH
Horizon Europe project
Research and Innovation Action
€ 8 000 000 budget
24 partners – 12 countries
01 November 2022 – 31 October 2026

15 sensor & system developments
3 patents
10 follow-up projects
20 AI algorithms/ aggregation methodologies

DATA COLLECTION ON 6 PILOT SITES PER YEAR
60 000 000 BROILERS
3 700 000 FATTENING PIGS

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AIM

Develop and offer a **cost-efficient solution to evaluate and improve the welfare of meat-producing animals** at a large scale, across Europe via **automated monitoring of animal-based welfare indicators (AWI) at the slaughterhouse** in order to give feedback and advice on best practices to those responsible for the various stages of production (farmer, catching team, transporter, slaughterhouse).

This approach will be developed and evaluated in close **collaboration with all actors involved, from primary producers up to policy makers and citizens.**

OBJECTIVES

- 1) Develop a **catalogue of AWI** for fattening pigs & broiler chickens collected **automatically** at the **slaughterhouse** or **routinely** on farm / transport
- 2) Develop **novel sensor systems** for collection of AWI and (AI) models to aggregate AWI for AW assessment at farm/chain/regional/national level
- 3) **Pilot the aWISH tools and integrated solution** in 6 regional production chains across Europe (FR, PL, ES, NL, AT, RS)
- 4) Develop a **feedback tool** for specific, real-time AW evaluation for each actor in the production cycle (farmer, catching team, transporter, slaughterhouse) and **best practice guides with advice** towards AW improvements
- 5) Investigate the **AW status and effect of AW improvement strategies (best practices)** on operator and regional/national level
- 6) Investigate the **socio-economic and environmental impact of AW improvement strategies**, including the **needs & barriers of all actors**
- 7) **Create awareness and engagement of the multi-actor community**, via a participative approach with all stakeholders involved

Funded by the
European Union

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